

Appendix: Working Group F: Framework for the value of research data

To define a framework for the assessment of the value of research data, working group F applies a three-step approach:

1. A series of brainstorming meetings and workshops within the working group and with some members of the national data management network to narrow down the *scope* for the work and identify some *relevant building blocks* for a conceptual framework.
Timeline: Q1-3 2024
2. A thorough *review of the literature* to identify (inter)national reports and activities relevant within the context of our defined scope, to contribute to a first version of a conceptual framework.
Timeline Q4 2024-Q1 2025
3. A *series of qualitative interviews* with stakeholders to collect input to adjust and/or expand our understanding of research data valuation, leading to a second version of a conceptual framework.
Timeline Q1-3 2025.

We expect to send the second version of our conceptual framework into a hearing with working group A-E.

Step 1: setting scope and determining building blocks

Scope

After a series of brainstorming meetings and workshops, working group F determined that the conceptual framework for the value of research data will limit itself to:

1. **Digital research data.**

In this project “research data” is defined as digital data collected, observed, generated, created or reused as part of research activities. This includes digital raw data, computer code, audio and video recordings, digital texts as well as the detailed records of these research outputs. It does *not* include physical material.

2. **Research activities at Danish universities.**

Working group F will focus on the value of research data as part of research activities at Danish Universities. This means that we will primarily focus on interviewing researchers at Danish universities and stakeholders that influence data management in projects carried out at Danish universities.

3. **Value parameters important for decision-making in research projects.**

Working group F aims to identify how the value of research data contributes to making data management decisions throughout the research project (see figure 1 below). The group will therefore use the research data lifecycle as the backbone structure for our interview guide.

4. **Stakeholders who influence decision-making.**

As a first priority, we aim to interview stakeholders who can influence decision-making

regarding the management of data and who are expected to have views on the value of data. For example: data value can be an important parameter to include when deciding on the level of protection required to safeguard the data (data lifecycle phase: store and secure). Besides researchers, we aim to interview security specialists at the universities. Likewise for data preservation decision-making, we aim to interview Rigsarkivet.

Figure 1 Phases on the research data lifecycle where assessments of data value can be relevant for decision-making in research data management actions.

Building blocks

Working group F has tentatively identified a set of building blocks that can determine the value of research data.

1. Factors that influence whether value can be obtained in the first place

Working group F proposes that some prerequisites need to be in place before research data will have value. For example, research data should be well-structured, well-described, accurate, trustworthy and complete.

2. The type of value that can be obtained

Working group F proposes a number of different ‘value types’ or categories that describe the value of research data, for example cultural value, scientific value, market value, replacement value and compliance value. How these value types are weighted depends on the party (stakeholder) setting the value.

3. Factors that influence the level of value

Working group F proposes factors that can have impact on the level of value obtained. These include reach of the data (the number of stakeholders with interest in the data), reusability of the data (FAIRness), timeliness (relevance of data at a certain point in time), exclusivity of the data (abundance of data when in demand) and innovation (value in relation to availability of methods, infrastructure for data processing).

For more information, please refer to Appendix 2, where we expand on these concepts.

It is important to note, that the primary purpose of defining a scope and building blocks was 1) to structure our groups' discussions, 2) to provide a starting point for the search terms to use when conducting a literature review, 3) to identify stakeholders to interview and 4) to provide a backbone to the interview guide we will develop.

The planned literature review and interviews will determine whether or to what degree our proposed building blocks can be used for the conceptual framework on data value, or whether they need to be replaced altogether.